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for a healthy future

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Annex 1.3

Interviewer Manual to the Basic Questionnaire for 2nd round priority substances

WP 7

Task 7.3

D 7.6

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1 Aims

The present manual contains instructions intended to facilitate the field work. This manual is designed specifically for interviewers in order to be considered as a reference tool at the time of collecting information. The success of the surveys depends largely on it.

Likewise, the manual provides a justification of the objective of each question included in the questionnaire developed by Task 7.3 to cover 2nd round of priority substances.

This questionnaire has been designed to collect all the necessary information concerning individual characteristics of the participants and different sources and routes of exposure to 2nd priority substances. This questionnaire is also aimed at characterizing, to the extent possible, the level of exposure to these substances. The questionnaire is divided into two parts:

a) General questions needed to characterize the study population, as well as to collect information on potential confounders. These questions are structured within the following sections: sociodemographic characteristics, residential environment and home exposures, dietary habits, lifestyles, occupational exposures and health status.

b) Questions specifically relevant for 2nd priority substances, included in separate questionnaires for each of these substances: Arsenic & its compounds, Acrylamide, Aprotic solvents, Diisocyanates, Lead & its compounds, Mercury, Mycotoxins, Pesticides and UV filters-Benzophenones.

This questionnaire aims to collect information in a standardized way from each participant, as this will enable to obtain comparable results across countries involved in the HBM4EU study.

2 Information for interviewers

To ensure that this questionnaire is administered in a standardized way, please follow the considerations listed below:

- ▶ This questionnaire only must be applied to the person selected to participate in HBM4EU study.
- ▶ Questions and responses must be literally read by the interviewers, always following the fixed order. To dispel misunderstanding among participants, please do speak clear and loud enough and at a normal rate to be adequately heard by the interviewee.
- ▶ The response given by the interviewee must be accepted by the interviewer. In those cases, where a certain response is not feasible or convincing the interviewer should formulate the question again to receive a new answer. If not, the given response will be finally accepted by the interviewer.
- ▶ All the questions of this questionnaire must be answered by the interviewee. In case the interviewee does not provide a precise response after a reasonable period of time, or refuse to answer, the question will be considered as "Don't know".

3 Interviewer manual for general questions

I. SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC SECTION

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. What is your birth date?</p>	<p>This question is essential to identify potential differences in human exposures, as well as susceptibility associated with the age. Potential determinant of exposure to arsenic & its compounds, acrylamide, aprotic solvents, diisocyanates, lead & its compounds, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV filters- Benzophenones (2nd priority substances).</p>	<p>Month and year of birth will be asked here.</p>
<p>2. Where were you, your parents and grandparents born?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on participants' country of origin, as it could lead to different exposure levels to priority substances (due to genetic characteristics, lifestyle or dietary habits, among others).</p>	<p>In this question, information on countries where the participants and their direct family members (parents and grandparents) were born will be asked for.</p>
<p>3. Which language(s) do you speak at home</p>	<p>Asking for languages spoken at home we can collect additional information on the origin of the participant and also on cultural factors.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the national language (or languages, for countries with several official languages) spoken at home. If other language(s) different from national languages is (are) spoken at home, specify which one(s).</p>
<p>4. How long have you been living in...? Please indicate the number of years (or months if less than 1 year)</p>	<p>This question is intended to gather information on internal and external migrations, since it could be associated with changes in chemical exposure levels.</p>	<p>According to geographical characteristics of each country, please ask for the length of time living in this country/region/province/municipality/current address. Select "Don't know" if the interviewee does not remember that time.</p>
<p>5. If you have lived in other households in the past 10 years, complete the following information for each address (starting with the current address and going back to complete the temporal frame)</p>	<p>This question provides information on residential history, which helps to identify the potential influence of the place of residence on the results of the study.</p>	<p>Please, provide complete information on this question. If address is not remembered, indicate at least the municipality or postal code. Regarding the period of time living in each place, try to collect information on how many months and years, if possible.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
6. What is the highest level of education you attained?	The level of education is a proxy of the socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. Determinant of exposure to arsenic & its compounds, acrylamide, aprotic solvents, diisocyanates, lead & its compounds, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV filters-Benzophenones (2 nd priority substances).	Please, indicate the level completed by the interviewee. When required, check the right category in Annex "International Standard Classification of Education" (at the end of this interviewer manual)
7. What is your current main labour status?	The labour status is also a proxy of the socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. Determinant of exposure to arsenic & its compounds, acrylamide, aprotic solvents, diisocyanates, lead & its compounds, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV filters-Benzophenones (2 nd priority substances).	Please note that this question is referred to the labour which the interviewee dedicates most of her/his time to.
8. Which of the following best describes your current professional category?	The professional category is also a proxy of the socio-economic situation, which could be used to develop an indicator of occupational social class. Determinant of exposure to arsenic & its compounds, acrylamide, aprotic solvents, diisocyanates, lead & its compounds, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV filters-Benzophenones (2 nd priority substances).	Please note that this question is referred to the current professional category in which the interviewee spends most of her/his time in. Check the ISCO 08 manual to answer this question (annex at the end of this interviewer manual).
9. Please, give us the following information on all members of your household	The number of people living in the same household, as well as their education, labour status and professional category, is an indicator of the socio economic situation of the household.	Please, complete the table with the information given for every household member (including members currently living at home, or outside but economically dependent from the household, e.g. students).
10. Could you provide the approximate range of your household 's total gross income?	The income level is an indicator of the socio economic status of the household. Determinant of exposure to arsenic & its compounds, acrylamide, aprotic solvents, diisocyanates, lead & its compounds, mercury, mycotoxins, pesticides and UV filters-Benzophenones (2 nd priority substances).	This question is referred to total annual gross incomes from all members of the household.

II. RESIDENTIAL ENVIRONMENT AND HOME EXPOSURES

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
1. In which area is your home located?	This question aims to characterize the environment where the participant lives, as differences could exist in human exposure associated with the area of residence.	This question has to be answered according to the area in which the home is located. Please, only one from the given options must be selected (best fit).
2. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?	It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to pollutants, which might lead to differences in human exposure levels. Likewise, this question provides information on the general characteristics of the living environment (e.g. heavily industrialized area...)	Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.
3. Which of the following options best describes your home...?	Asking for home types allows gathering additional information on the characteristics of the dwelling and the environment where the participant live. Moreover, the home type could contribute to different exposure to contaminants (e.g. floor level, isolation...)	Indicate the option that best fits from the given options. When necessary, specify other home types. Please note that semi-detached house is a single-family home that is built to share one common wall with the adjacent home, having both of them the same design. On the other hand, townhouses are traditionally row houses with two or more floors, where homes are connected, on both sides and on all levels.
4. Do you know approximately when was your home built?	Home's age is a direct indicator of the indoor environment and also of the materials and compounds used for building. Since some compounds have been banned and others have emerged, this question will provide information on the potential contribution of home's age on environmental exposures levels.	Please select the year range where the year of building is more likely included, according to the participant's answer. If the interviewee has not a clear idea or a reference of the age of building, then select Don't Know.
5. What is the living surface (in m²) of your house?	The home surface, together with the number of household members, provides information on the socio-economic status of the participant. Furthermore, this surface might also affect the indoor concentration of certain compounds, which leads to differences in levels of exposure.	This question refers to indoor living spaces (terraces, gardens... should not be included). Participants can provide an estimation or rounding answers if they do not know exactly the home surface.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
6. Do you have any of the following problems in your home?	Mould or mildew on walls and water damage, among others, are frequent domestic problems which can provide information on the quality of the living environment, as well as on participant's socio-economic status.	Complete the table with the information on domestic problems given by the interviewee.
7. How often is general cleaning done in your home?	House cleaning is associated with the concentration of substances, including chemical pollutants inside home. This variable might affect human exposure indoors, since house cleaning involves the mobilization and elimination of dust-borne chemicals deposited in floor, windows, etc.	Please note that general cleaning refers to a wide cleaning in the whole dwelling involving floors, dust, regardless of the person involved on this task.
8. Are you in charge of general cleaning of your home?	As mentioned above, house cleaning might affect human exposure to substances accumulated indoors, especially by those in charge of the general cleaning, due to their direct contact.	Please, specify the contribution of the interviewee to the general cleaning of the house (if he/she has a partial contribution, ask for an estimation of the percentage of the workload usually done).
9. Do you use a vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? If yes, please, specify type of vacuum cleaner and use frequency	The use of vacuum cleaner for house cleaning involves the mobilization of substances accumulated in domestic dust. This might affect the concentrations of circulating compounds inside home and therefore, the exposure of residents to these compounds.	Please, indicate if a vacuum cleaner is used for house cleaning. When appropriate, specify the frequency of use, as well as the type of filter. Note that water filters refer to those vacuum cleaners having a container for water, while air filters do not need water for working but a bag or a tank where the dust is accumulated.
10. How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please, specify frequency of ventilation (months/year in which mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season)	Ventilation at home (mechanical or manual) is related with the exchange of circulating compounds, affecting to indoor concentrations of these compounds at home, and consequently to human exposure levels.	Please, ask for ways of the ventilation of home, and their frequency of use. Please note that mechanical ventilation usually entails the presence of electromechanical systems (e.g. fans) to drive air flow inside and outside home. In case this mechanical system is automatically working, then indicate Always working in the questionnaire.

III. DIETARY HABITS

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>This question is necessary to assess the overall dietary habits of participants, as well as to identify the main predictors of the exposure to 2nd round of priority substances related to the diet.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food you eat, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Annex to this manual "Food serving sizes gallery" to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual). Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
<p>2. Do you consume dietary supplements (e.g. vitamins and minerals)? If so, please indicate frequency, starting date and finishing date (if the use has finished).</p>	<p>Human metabolism of some xenobiotics could be affected/modulated by the concentration of vitamins.</p>	<p>Information on vitamins and supplements (not for medicines), has to be collected here. When appropriate (e.g. a product not included in the listed options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't know.</p>
<p>3. How much water do you drink on average each day? (Consider also hot beverages and soups!)</p>	<p>This question evaluates the amount of water consumed daily by the interviewees.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the current amount of water consumption. Also consider any other beverages you drink at home and outside home, including hot beverages, tea, coffee and soup.</p>
<p>7. What is the main source of your drinking water? And cooking water?</p>	<p>This question is essential to understand what kind of water is consumed most frequently by study participants because the different sources of water have their own bromatological and chemical composition. Together with the home address it provides valuable exposure information.</p>	<p>This question refers to water consumed at home or elsewhere (e.g., tap water, bottled water). Consider also water use to prepare hot beverages (tea, coffee), and for preparing meals. Please, only indicate the main source of drinking and cooking water.</p>
<p>8. Do you use water purification devices or water filtering systems for your drinking water? And cooking water?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the kind of filters used by the participants at home because filters modify and purify water and consequently they can influence the levels of chemicals of interest.</p>	<p>This refers to any water treatments done at home, do not include treatments performed by the municipality.</p>

IV. LIFESTYLE

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen.</p>		<p>Please, indicate the situation of the participant in relation to smoking habits. Specify the type of product and the frequency of smoking (occasionally, daily and ex-smokers). If the participant has never smoked, 'no' can be ticked under point 1.1 and skip the remaining parts of the question.</p>
<p>2. How many people living in this house smoke regularly (indoors)? For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked indoors per day</p>	<p>Information on smoking habits and passive exposure to tobacco smoke has to be collected since these are well known sources of exposure to a wide variety of chemical substances, as an important confounder.</p>	<p>Please, complete this table for all of the household members that smoke inside the home.</p>
<p>3. Do people who visit this house smoke indoor?</p>		<p>Here, ask for the frequency in which people visiting the house smoke (indoors)</p>
<p>4. How long, on a daily average, do you usually spend in the following indoor places where people smoke?</p>		<p>Here it is important to ask only for these indoor places where people smoke, not for general indoor places.</p>
<p>5. From the following list of alcoholic beverages, please, indicate your frequency of consumption during the previous 12 months?</p>	<p>Alcohol has been identified as an important confounder in many epidemiological studies. Hence, information on alcohol consumption in the last year has to be collected.</p>	<p>Indicate the frequency of alcoholic beverages consumption, indicating the volume of each drink as accurately as possible.</p>
<p>6. Which of the following options best describes your current physical exercise? Please do not take into account your physical activity at work</p>	<p>This question aims to collect information on general physical exercise. Physical exercise might affect some factors related to metabolism of xenobiotics in humans, as has been observed in epidemiological studies, which could lead to differences in exposure levels to these compounds.</p>	<p>This question includes information on overall physical exercise, excluding working activity. Please, note that intensive exercise refers to any sweating activity that also makes breathing harder.</p>
<p>7. How much time do you spend on average in the following places (referred to workdays and weekends)?</p>	<p>The time spent on a daily basis in different environments will provide essential information on potential sources of exposure to contaminants in humans, as well as on their contribution on total exposure burden.</p>	<p>Please, compile information on time spent in each of the given environments, during workdays and weekends. Time should refer to an average of time based on the daily habits of the interviewee. 'In your car' refers to the total time spent seated in the car with the doors closed, no matter if the engine is turned on or not.</p>

V. OCCUPATION

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. Please, indicate the sector of industry/workplace in which you are currently working (refer to annex this interviewer manual): If other, please specify:</p>	<p>The sector of industry is needed to classify the field of work.</p>	<p>Annex to this interviewer manual: The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE (NACE Rev. 2) at the end of this document (main classes).</p>
<p>2. Please, describe your current job:</p>	<p>Job description gives information about the type of work where possible exposures could occur.</p>	<p>Detailed description of work tasks is important to correctly interpret the participants' exposure conditions.</p>
<p>3. How long have you been doing this job? Specify years (or months if less than one year)</p>	<p>Length of time working is important when assessing effects of occupational exposures</p>	<p>Total working time in this job in years and months is asked.</p>
<p>4. Which of the following substances are you exposed to in your job?</p>	<p>This question is essential to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>It is important to let participants enough time to think about the possible exposure to these substances. Category of chemicals is listed in questions 4.1 - 4.27 considering various exposure conditions. Some of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU are mentioned separately in a specified exposure category.</p>
<p>4.1. Oil, gasoline, or diesel</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g., oil refining/ petrochemical plants/ petroleum refinery, garage work, contaminated soil renovation).</p>
<p>4.2. Creosote, creosote oil, coal tar</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g. creosote work, wood impregnation, pillar work, rail work, contaminated soil renovation)</p>
<p>4.3. Bitumen, bitumen products</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g. road paving, bitumen work, bitumen roofing, waterproofing, contaminated soil renovation)</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
4.4. Combustion products, including gasoline/diesel exhausts, ash or soot	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as and to avoid possible bias.	Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with combustion products (e.g. aluminum production, chimney sweeping, coking plants, firefighting/ fire practice/ fire prevention training, foundry industry, garage work, heating/thermal power plants, metallurgic industry, mining, vehicle inspection, vehicle depots, waste incineration)
4.5. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), if not included in other substance group/categories	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Other possible sources of PAH exposure. In case some specific PAHs are used, identification of PAH compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.) is informative in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.6. Metallic dust	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with metallic dust. Identification of metals/substances in dust (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Metallic dust could be a source of exposure to hazardous metals including 2 nd priority substances.
4.7. Mercury	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Mercury is one of the 2 nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury or mercury compounds. In the case of mercury compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
4.8. Lead	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Lead is one of the 2 nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury or mercury compounds. In the case of mercury compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
4.9. Cadmium	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work where you come into contact with cadmium or cadmium compounds. In case of cadmium compounds, specify individual compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
4.10. Chromium (VI)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work where you come into contact with chromium or chromium compounds. In the case of chromium compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
4.11. Other metals	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Identification of metals and metal compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.12. Pharmaceuticals	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the effective drug and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.13. Paints/ coatings	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the paint and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.14. Printing inks	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the ink and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with printing inks (e.g. ink production, printing industry, other job, which?).
4.15. Dyes, azo dyes and pigments (tattoo inks, sulphur dyes, indigo compounds)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the dye or pigment and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.16. Diisocyanates, 4,4'-Methylenediphenyl diisocyanate (MDI)-based lacquers, foams and adhesives, toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and MDI or TDI-based polyurethane polymers	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Diisocyanates are one of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Specification of each of the diisocyanates (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Some anilines (e.g. methylenedianiline (MDA) and toluenediamine (TDA)) are metabolites of diisocyanates. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with diisocyanates.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
4.17. Varnishes	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of varnishes and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.18. Solvents	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of solvents and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.19. Plasticisers	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the plasticisers (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Plasticisers could contain e.g. phthalates, which are 1 st priority substances under HBM4EU.
4.20. Pesticides, biocides or disinfection products (herbicides, fungicides, insecticides or bactericides)	The question aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Pesticides are one of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Specification of each of the pesticides and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.21. Cosmetics or hair treatment products (hair dyes, etc.)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of cosmetics or hair treatment products/hair dyes and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.22. Anilines (e.g. aniline, 4,4'-methylenedianiline (=4,4'-MDA), 4,4'-methylenebis[2-chloroaniline] (= MOCA), o- and p-toluidine, p-phenylenediamine (= p-PDA), 1,3-diphenylguanidine), if not included in other substance/ group	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Other possible sources of exposure to anilines (especially aniline, 4,4'-MDA, MOCA, o- and p-toluidine, p-PDA, 1,3-diphenylguanidine). In case some specific anilines are used, identification of each of the aniline (name, CAS-number, etc.) is informative in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.23. Rubber chemicals	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Identification of specific rubber chemicals (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with rubber chemicals.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
4.24. Flame retardants	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Identification of each of the flame retardants and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.25. Nanomaterials	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of nanomaterials and nanoparticles (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.26. Photoresist/antireflective coatings	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of each of the photoresist/antireflective coatings and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.27. Other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (e.g. contaminated soil renovation)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
4.28. Mycotoxins (working with flours as bakery, waste Management, farming activities as animal production, greenhouse and others)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Mycotoxins are one of the 2 nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury or mercury compounds. In the case of mercury compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
4.29. Other compounds	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of each other compound used (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>5. Please, indicate the main work tasks/activities that you perform regularly: Task/activity 1, 2 and 3:</p> <p>* Duration of the tasks (hours in a work shift):</p> <p>* Frequency of the tasks (days/week or days/month):</p> <p>* Chemicals/substances produced, used or handled (please, refer to category list of question 4):</p> <p>* Use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) (please, specify the type):</p> <p>* Availability of collective protective measures (please, specify the type):</p>	<p>The main work tasks/activities give insight into participants' regular exposure conditions.</p> <p>Duration provides information about the total length of possible exposure in that task per workday.</p> <p>Frequency provides information about frequency of possible exposure in that task on a workweek or month basis.</p> <p>This question provides information about possible sources of exposure in main work tasks/activities. This question provides information on the PPE used in that task, which is an important exposure modifier.</p> <p>This question provides information on collective protective measures in that task, which are also important exposure modifiers.</p>	<p>There are three main work tasks in the questionnaire and the following five questions are asked in each of them.</p> <p>This is the average time devoted to that task every workday (less than one hour could be expressed as minutes).</p> <p>Frequency is expressed as days per week or days per month. Please, fulfill how many days and circle or write down the selection, week or month. Referred to the category list of question 4. If there is answered "yes" or "specify" -selection is fulfilled.</p> <p>Please, specify the type of PPE (e.g. respirator and type, hand protection/gloves, protective clothing, eye protection).</p> <p>Please, specify the type of collective protective measures used (e.g. general ventilation, local ventilation, compartmentalization).</p> <p>Please, collect the above information from each of the tasks developed by the interviewee (1, 2, 3 or more, according to the individual case).</p>
<p>6. Do you use Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)?</p>	<p>This question provides information on PPE used in general.</p>	<p>Please, specify the type of PPE (e.g. respirator and type, hand protection/gloves, protective clothing, eye protection).</p>
<p>7. In the working environment in which you perform working tasks/activities are there technical risk management measures (e.g. local exhaust ventilation, compartmentalisation of the exposure source...) available?</p>	<p>This question provides information on collective protective measures in the workplace in general.</p>	<p>Please, specify the type of measures used (e.g. general ventilation, local ventilation, compartmentalization)</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>8. Are you subjected to a health surveillance program at work? If yes: Does the health surveillance program to which you are subjected include biological monitoring (measurement of chemicals or their metabolites in e.g. blood or urine samples)?</p>	<p>This question provides information whether biological monitoring is carried out.</p>	<p>If answer is yes: -What chemicals/substances have been monitored (if known, please specify the CAS number)? Specification of the biological matrix used for the analysis (e.g. chromium in urine) is also essential. -How often is the biological monitoring carried out?</p>
<p>Other information on occupational exposure: 9.. Are your family/household members working with chemicals in their job?</p>	<p>This question provides additional information on possible exposures.</p>	<p>If yes, specify: -How many members are working with chemicals? -Which chemicals are involved?</p>
Occupational history		
<p>1. Please, fill the following questions for each of your previous jobs in the past 25 years.</p>	<p>The industry sector is needed to classify the field of work. Job description gives information about the type of work where possible exposures can occur. The working period is important when assessing effects of exposure.</p>	<p>Please see Annex to this interviewer manual: The Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community, abbreviated as NACE (NACE Rev. 2) at the end of this document (main classes and sub- classification). Detailed description of work tasks is important to correctly interpret the participants' exposure conditions. The total working time in this job (in years and months) is asked.</p>
<p>2. Did you come into contact with the following substances on your job?</p>	<p>This question is essential to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>It is important to let participants enough time to think about the possible exposure to these substances. Category of chemicals is listed in questions 4.1 - 4.27 considering various exposure conditions. Some of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU are mentioned separately in a specified exposure category.</p>
<p>2.1. Oil, gasoline, or diesel</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g., oil refining/ petrochemical plants/ petroleum refinery, garage work, contaminated soil renovation).</p>
<p>2.2. Creosote, creosote oil, coal tar</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g. creosote work, wood impregnation, pillar work, rail work, contaminated soil renovation)</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2.3. Bitumen, bitumen products	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with these substances (e.g. road paving, bitumen work, bitumen roofing, waterproofing, contaminated soil renovation)
2.4. Combustion products, including gasoline/diesel exhausts, ash or soot	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as and to avoid possible bias.	Please, select from the list or otherwise specify the work where you come into contact with combustion products (e.g. aluminum production, chimney sweeping, coking plants, firefighting/ fire practice/ fire prevention training, foundry industry, garage work, heating/thermal power plants, metallurgic industry, mining, vehicle inspection, vehicle depots, waste incineration)
2.5. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs),if not included in other substance group/categories	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Other possible sources of PAH exposure. In case some specific PAHs are used, identification of PAH compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.) is informative in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.6. Metallic dust	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with metallic dust. Identification of metals/substances in dust (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Metallic dust could be a source of exposure to hazardous metals including 2 nd priority substances.
2.7. Mercury	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Mercury is one of the 2 nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury or mercury compounds. In the case of mercury compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
2.8. Lead	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Lead is one of the 2 nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury or mercury compounds. In the case of mercury compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2.9. Cadmium	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work where you come into contact with cadmium or cadmium compounds. In case of cadmium compounds, specify individual compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
2.10. Chromium (VI)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Please, specify the work where you come into contact with chromium or chromium compounds. In the case of chromium compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
2.11. Other metals	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Identification of metals and metal compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.12. Pharmaceuticals	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the effective drug and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.13. Paints/ coatings	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the paint and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.14. Printing inks	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and of biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the ink and its ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with printing inks (e.g. ink production, printing industry, other job, which?).
2.15. Dyes, azo dyes and pigments (tattoo inks, sulphur dyes, indigo compounds)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the dye or pigment and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2.16. Diisocyanates,4,4'-Methylenediphenyl diisocyanate (MDI)-based lacquers, foams and adhesives, toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and MDI or TDI-based polyurethane polymers	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Diisocyanates are one of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Specification of each of the diisocyanates (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Some anilines (e.g.methylenedianiline (MDA) and toluenediamine (TDA)) are metabolites of diisocyanates. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with diisocyanates.
2.17. Varnishes	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of varnishes and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.18. Solvents	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of solvents and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.19. Plasticisers	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of the plasticisers (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Plasticisers could contain e.g. phthalates, which are 1 st priority substances under HBM4EU.
2.20. Pesticides, biocides or disinfection products (herbicides, fungicides, insecticides or bactericides)	The question aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Pesticides are one of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU.	Specification of each of the pesticides and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.
2.21. Cosmetics or hair treatment products (hair dyes etc.)	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.	Specification of cosmetics or hair treatment products/hair dyes and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2.22. Anilines (e.g. aniline, 4,4'-methylenedianiline (=4,4'-MDA), 4,4'-methylenebis[2-chloroaniline] (= MOCA), o- and p-toluidine, p-phenylenediamine (= p-PDA), 1,3-diphenylguanidine), if not included in other substance/group</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Other possible sources of exposure to anilines (especially aniline, 4,4'-MDA, MOCA, o- and p-toluidine, p-PDA, 1,3-diphenylguanidine). In case some specific anilines are used, identification of each of the aniline (name, CAS-number, etc.) is informative in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>2.23. Rubber chemicals</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Identification of specific rubber chemicals (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire. Please, specify the work where you come into contact with rubber chemicals.</p>
<p>2.24. Flame retardants</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Identification of each of the flame retardants and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>2.25. Nanomaterials</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Specification of nanomaterials and nanoparticles (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>2.26. Photoresist/antireflective coatings</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Specification of each of the photoresist/antireflective coatings and their ingredients (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>2.27. Other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (e.g. contaminated soil renovation)</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Specification of other hazardous materials, hazardous waste or other chemicals (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>2.28 Mycotoxins (working with flours as bakery, waste Management, farming activities as animal production, greenhouse and others)</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias. Mycotoxins are one of the 2nd priority substances under HBM4EU.</p>	

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2.29. Other compounds</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire and biological monitoring as well as to avoid possible bias.</p>	<p>Specification of each other compound used (name, CAS-number, etc.) is essential in order to correctly interpret the results of the questionnaire.</p>
<p>3. Were you subjected to a health surveillance program at work in the past?</p> <p>If yes: Did this health surveillance program to which you were subjected include biological monitoring (measurement of chemicals or their metabolites in e.g. blood or urine samples)?</p>	<p>This question provides information on whether biological monitoring had been carried out in previous jobs.</p>	<p>If answer is yes: -What chemicals/substances were monitored (if known, please specify the CAS number)? Specification of analyte and biological material (e.g. chromium in urine) is also essential. -How often was biological monitoring carried out?</p>

VI. HEALTH

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
1. Anthropometric measurements	Anthropometric measurements are indicators of body composition. The BMI has been shown to be significantly correlated with exposure to some phthalates.	Record the self-reported height in cm without shoes. Record the self-reported weight in kg without clothes and shoes.
2. Weight change	Weight change is an indicator of intended and unintended changes in body weight.	If the interviewee reports that his/her weight has not changed during the past year, skip questions 2.2 and 2.3. For 2.2 and 2.3 weight change is recorded in kg.
3. Do you have or have you ever had any of the following diseases or conditions, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed.	The information about diagnosed diseases is an indicator about disease prevalence and disease history.	The interviewee is asked to provide answer to all diseases on the list and if he/she says "Yes", then ask and record the age when the disease was diagnosed for the first time. If the interviewee says that he/she has been diagnosed for any other disease(s) not listed, this should be recorded at the end under 'Other diseases or conditions'
4. If you answered "Yes" for cancer, please specify what kind of cancer	The information about cancer types is an indicator of specific cancer prevalence.	This question is asked only for those who self-reported to have or have had any cancer. In case of having had more than one cancer at different sites, record all different cancers reported.
5. During the past two weeks, have you used any medicines that were prescribed for you by a doctor?	This question provides information about medication use for three defined diseases: hypertension, high cholesterol and diabetes. This information is needed, in addition that from health examinations, to define whether a person has hypertension, elevated cholesterol or diabetes.	This question asks use of medication for hypertension, high blood cholesterol levels and diabetes.
5.1 Which medicines prescribed for you by a doctor you have used in the past two weeks? Please, indicate the commercial name of the medicine, the indication, as well as the strength of the drug, dose and frequency of use	This question provides information about medication use in general. This information is needed to define does person have a specific disease together with information about diagnosed diseases.	This question asks about the use of medicines. All medicines prescribed by a doctor and used in the past two weeks should be recorded as accurately as the interviewee recall this information. Participants will be invited to check the package leaflet of the medicinal product before answering questions concerning medicines.
6. Have you been vaccinated for?	This question provides information about vaccination status.	Replies to all defined vaccinations are required.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
7. Are you pregnant at present?	This question provides information about pregnancy status of female participants. It is needed to identify pregnant women as they may need to be treated separately in some analysis.	This question is asked for women only. Question is asked from women younger than 45 years.
8. Have you ever been pregnant?	This question provides information on the number of pregnancies.	This question is asked for women only. If the interviewee replies that she has ever been pregnant, ask the number of pregnancies including possible current pregnancy, live births, miscarriages, stillbirths, tubal pregnancies and abortions.
9. Please, complete the following information for each of your pregnancies	This question provides detailed information on each pregnancy.	This question is asked for women only. For each pregnancy, information is needed about the outcome: abortion, live birth, polyembryonic or birth defects have to be recorded.
10. Are you breast feeding or had breastfed? If so, please indicate the length of breastfeeding.	This question provides information about breast feeding history, since it could affect the concentrations of certain compounds in humans.	This question is asked from women only. Women with several children have to specify total months of breastfeeding.
11. Have there been time period when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?	This question provides information on fertility problems.	This question is asked for women only. This question refers to attempts to get pregnant without success or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies 'Yes', the further question to ask is when was the last time this happened (in years) is asked.
12. Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?	This question provides information on fertility problems.	This question is asked for women only.
12.1 What was the reason for your infertility?	This question provides information on type of the fertility problems.	This question is asked for women only. This question refers to the fertility problems listed in the questionnaire.
13. Which of the following options best describe your menstrual cycle?	Information on menstrual cycle and menopause will be collected here, since it could affect the bioaccumulation of substances in women.	This question is asked from women only. Please, collect information on the current situation. Menopause refers to the absence of menstrual periods for 12 consecutive months

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
14. Have there been time period when you have attempted to have a child but have not succeeded or it took over 12 months to succeed?	This question provides information about fertility problems.	This question is asked from men only. This question refers to attempts to get pregnant without success or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies 'Yes', further question on when was the last time this happened (in years) is asked.
15. Have you ever been examined or been treated for infertility?	This question provides information regarding fertility problems.	This question is asked from men only. This question refers to attempts to have a child without getting it or when it took over 12 months to succeed. If person replies 'Yes', the further question to ask is when was the last time this happened (in years).
15.1 What was the reason for your infertility?	This question provides information on fertility problems.	This question is asked for men only.

4 Interviewer manual for specific questions on 2nd round priority substances

4.1 Arsenic & its compounds

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?	It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to arsenic.	Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.
Diet		
1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?	This question aims to identify the main dietary predictors of the exposure to arsenic.	Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food you eat, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Annex to this manual "Food serving sizes gallery" to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual). Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.
Lifestyle		
1. In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen.	Information on smoking habits and passive exposure to tobacco smoke has to be collected since these are sources of exposure to arsenic.	Please, indicate the situation of the participant in relation to smoking habits. Specify the type of product and the frequency of smoking (occasionally, daily and ex-smokers). If the participant has never smoked, 'no' can be ticked under point 1.1 and skip the remaining parts of the question.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2. How many people living in this house smoke regularly (indoors)? For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked indoors per day.</p>		<p>Please, complete this table for all of the household members that smoke inside the home.</p>
<p>3. Did you carry out one of the following DIY activities or hobbies and/or did you use one of the following products performing these DIY activities or hobbies in the last month? (please, do not count your professional activity)</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to arsenic. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to arsenic.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know. For those questions covering the use of inks (e.g. tattoos), please note that they refer to people using these substances (e.g. tattoos artists) but not to people receiving a tattoo.</p>
<p>4. How often did you use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand you mostly use.</p>	<p>Personal care products and cosmetics are widely used. Complete information on the use of these products is needed to a proper characterization of the exposure to arsenic in humans. The use of certain bleaching creams and other cosmetics could be associated with the exposure to arsenic.</p>	<p>Complete information on personal care products and cosmetic used by the interviewee in the last month has to be collected. For each listed product, please indicate yes/no, and the commercial brand for those used by the interviewees. If the interviewee cannot give an answer for a product, please invite him/her to check whether the mentioned product is available at home at the time of the interview. The best would be to show a list of the cosmetic products in question and let the participant to read it along with the interviewer. This would make it easier and quicker to point out the cosmetic items used.</p>
<p>5. If sun cream or sun screen is used: which type of sun cream or sunscreen do you normally use?</p>	<p>Information on the use of sun screen will be collected, since arsenic compounds can be found in these personal care products.</p>	<p>Information on the type(s) of sun cream usually used will be collected here.</p>
<p>6. If sun screen is used: how do you apply sunscreen that you usually use? As a...</p>		<p>Information on how the sun cream is usually applied will be collected here.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>7. What type of personal care products do you mostly use?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the potential effect of using chemical and eco-friendly products on the exposure levels to arsenic.</p>	<p>Please note that <i>Eco-friendly</i> products refer to those products without chemical substances in their composition (or reduced concentrations). They can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate chemical from <i>eco-friendly</i> products. If the interviewee does not have a clear response about the origin of these products, then select Don't Know.</p>
Occupation		
<p>1. Arsenic exposure: from the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to arsenic.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with arsenic and its compounds. In the case of arsenic compounds, specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>2. Arsenic exposure history: in your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)?</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to arsenic.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>
Health		
<p>1. Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?</p>	<p>It is important to collect information on those symptoms found to be associated with the exposure to arsenic.</p>	<p>The timeframe of this question refers to the last 5 years. Please, specify if the interviewee suffered any of this symptoms, if yes, specify the frequency.</p>

4.2 Acrylamide

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
<p>1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to acrylamide.</p>	<p>Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>
Diet		
<p>1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?</p> <p>2. During the past 4 weeks, how often did you consume any of the following beverages?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the main dietary predictors of the exposure to acrylamide.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food/beverage you eat/drink, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...) Please, show Annex to this manual "Food serving sizes gallery" to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual). Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
Lifestyle		
<p>1. In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen.</p>	<p>Information on smoking habits and passive exposure to tobacco smoke has to be collected</p>	<p>Please, indicate the situation of the participant in relation to smoking habits. Specify the type of product and the frequency of smoking (occasionally, daily and ex-smokers). If the participant has never smoked, 'no' can be ticked under point 1.1 and skip the remaining parts of the question.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2. How many people living in this house smoke regularly (indoors)? For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked indoors per day	since these are sources of exposure to acrylamide.	Please, complete this table for all of the household members that smoke inside the home.
3. How often do you (or any family member) cook using...?	Cooking at high temperatures and exposure to smoke from cooking are found to be related to acrylamides' emissions.	Please, indicate which items are used at home for cooking (by the interviewee or other family member). Multiple answers are possible.
4. Do you have a ventilation hood above the stove?		Please, provide information on the presence of a hood above the stove.

4.3 Aprotic solvents

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?	It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to aprotic solvents.	Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.
Occupation		
1. Aprotic solvent exposure (DMA= N,N-dimethylacetamide): From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with aprotic solvents. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2. Aprotic solvent exposure (DMF = N,N-dimethylformamide): From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with aprotic solvents. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>3. Aprotic solvent exposure (NMP = 1-methyl-2-pyrrolidone): From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with aprotic solvents. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>4. Aprotic solvent exposure history (DMA): In your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities? (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures).</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>
<p>5. Aprotic solvent exposure history (DMF): In your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities? (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>
<p>6. Aprotic solvent (NMP) exposure history: In your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities? (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures).</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to aprotic solvents.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>

4.4 Diisocyanates

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
<p>1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to diisocyanates.</p>	<p>Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible.</p> <p>If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home".</p> <p>When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>
Lifestyle		
<p>1. Did you carry out any of the following activities as DIY activities or hobbies and/or were you exposed to any of these substances in these activities in the last month? (please, do not count your professional activity)</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to diisocyanates. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to diisocyanates.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month.</p> <p>For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know. For those questions covering the use of inks (e.g. tattoos), please note that they refer to people using these substances (e.g. tattoos artists) but not to people receiving a tattoo.</p>
Occupation		
<p>1. Diisocyanate exposure: From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures.</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to diisocyanates.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with aprotic solvents. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2. Diisocyanate exposure history: In your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities? (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures).	The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to diisocyanates.	Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.

4.5 Lead & its compounds

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?	It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to lead & its compounds	Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.
2. Which is the material most used for pipes of water supply lines in your home?	Information on the type of pipes of water supply is required, since having lead pipes at home could be a source of exposure to this substance.	Please, specify the main material which pipes are made of.
3. Please, complete the following information about redecorations and renovations made in your home. Has your home been...?	Renovations and redecorations at home entail the use of a wide of variety of compounds, such as paints, varnish, metals, and plastics, among others. This could contribute to chemical exposure, including exposure to lead ant is compounds, in people living in houses where recent renovations and redecorations were conducted.	Please, consider only renovations conducted in the last 2 years, and redecorations in the last year. Renovations refer to major changes made at home for a better state, such as removing floor or windows, rebuilding walls or roof, remodelling kitchen or bathroom... Redecorations refer to changes in decorative scheme or appearance, such as applying paint, varnish, changing wallpapers, among others.
Diet		

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the main dietary predictors of the exposure to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food/beverage you eat/drink, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...)</p> <p>Please, show Annex to this manual "Food serving sizes gallery" to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual). Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
<p>2. What materials do you use as cookware for cooking and frying (e.g. pots, pans, fryer, robots, making bread machine etc.)</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to lead due to the migration of this substance from cookware to food.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances, other ones such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>
<p>3. Do you use the following containers for keeping food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to lead due to the migration of this substance from containers to food.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances, other ones such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>
<p>4. Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating food in the microwave oven? If yes: how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to lead due to the migration of this substance from containers to food.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of materials, most of them considered as possible sources of prioritized substances, other ones such as aluminum or glass are possible.</p>
Lifestyle		
<p>1. In relation to smoking habits, which of the following options best describes your situation? Please, specify all the information for the situation chosen.</p>	<p>Information on smoking habits and passive exposure to tobacco smoke has to be collected since these are sources of exposure to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the situation of the participant in relation to smoking habits. Specify the type of product and the frequency of smoking (occasionally, daily and ex-smokers). If the participant has never smoked, 'no' can be ticked under point 1.1 and skip the remaining parts of the question.</p>
<p>2. How many people living in this house smoke regularly (indoors)? For each of them, please indicate the average number of cigarettes smoked indoors per day.</p>		<p>Please, complete this table for all of the household members that smoke inside the home.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>3. How often did you use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand you mostly use.</p>	<p>Personal care products and cosmetics are widely used. Complete information on the use of these products is needed to a proper characterization of the exposure to lead and its compounds in humans. The use of certain bleaching creams and other cosmetics could be associated with the exposure to lead.</p>	<p>Complete information on personal care products and cosmetic used by the interviewee in the last month has to be collected. For each listed product, please indicate yes/no, and the commercial brand for those used by the interviewees. If the interviewee cannot give an answer for a product, please invite him/her to check whether the mentioned product is available at home at the time of the interview. The best would be to show a list of the cosmetic products in question and let the participant to read it along with the interviewer. This would make it easier and quicker to point out the cosmetic items used.</p>
<p>4. What type of personal care products do you mostly use?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the potential effect of using chemical and eco-friendly products on the exposure levels to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please note that <i>Eco-friendly</i> products refer to those products without chemical substances in their composition (or reduced concentrations). They can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate chemical from <i>eco-friendly</i> products. If the interviewee does not have a clear response about the origin of these products, then select Don't Know.</p>
<p>5. Did you carry out one of the following DIY activities or hobbies and/or did you use one of the following products performing these DIY activities or hobbies in the last month? (please, do not count your professional activity).</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to lead and its compounds. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know.</p>
<p>6. Do you regularly wear plastic or rubber shoes such as e.g. flip-flops, beach shoes, swimming shoes, Crocs ® or clogs without socks?.</p>	<p>In certain cases, rubber shoes could contain lead. Direct contact with (sweating) skin can therefore be a source of exposure to this substance.</p>	<p>Please, ask for the regular use of the type of plastic or rubber shoes mentioned. The use is limited to cases wearing shoes without socks.</p>
<p>Occupation</p>		

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures.</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with lead and its compounds. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>2. Lead exposure history: In your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities? (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures.</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to lead and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>
<p>Health</p>		
<p>1. Do you have or have you ever had anemia, diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p>	<p>It is important to collect information on those symptoms found to be associated with the exposure to lead.</p>	<p>These questions refer to those health problems diagnosed by a medical doctor.</p>
<p>2. Do you have or have you ever had digestive system disorders (constipation, nausea and poor appetite), diagnosed by a medical doctor? If yes, please specify how old you were when this was first diagnosed</p>		
<p>3. Do you have or ever had amalgam fillings or dental sealant in your teeth?</p>	<p>This question is used to identify persons with amalgam fillings and dental sealant. They may need to be treated separately in some analysis. Amalgam fillings could be a source of exposure to metals.</p>	<p>Please note that a filling is expected to last for as many as ten years, whereas the average life expectancy of a dental sealant is no longer than a year. Sealants are usually provided to children. If person reports that he/she has any amalgam fillings, the number of teeth which have the filling should be recorded as the time when the filling was last time placed/removed.</p>
<p>4. Do you have any artificial joints, pins, plates, metal suture material, or other types of metal objects in your body? (Do not include piercings, crowns, dental braces or retainers, shrapnel, or bullets.)</p>	<p>This question is used to identify persons with artificial joints etc. in their body. These may need to be treated separately in some analysis.</p>	<p>The interviewee should answer "Yes" if he/she has any of the listed objects in their body.</p>

4.6 Mercury & its organic compounds

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
<p>1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to mercury & its compounds</p>	<p>Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible.</p> <p>If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home".</p> <p>When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>
Diet		
<p>1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the main dietary predictors of the exposure to mercury and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet.</p> <p>Think about all the food/beverage you eat/drink, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...)</p> <p>Please, show Annex to this manual "Food serving sizes gallery" to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual).</p> <p>Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
Lifestyle		

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. Did you carry out one of the following DIY activities or hobbies and/or did you use one of the following products performing these DIY activities or hobbies in the last month? (please, do not count your professional activity)</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to lead and its compounds. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to mercury and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know. For those questions covering the use of inks (e.g. tattoos), please note that they refer to people using these substances (e.g. tattoos artists) but not to people receiving a tattoo.</p>
Occupation		
<p>1. From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to mercury and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with mercury and its compounds. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>2. Mercury exposure history: in your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)?</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to mercury and its compounds.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>
Health		
<p>1. Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?</p>	<p>It is important to collect information on those symptoms found to be associated with the exposure to mercury.</p>	<p>The timeframe of this question refers to the last 5 years. Please, specify if the interviewee suffered any of this symptoms, if yes, specify the frequency.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2. Do you have or ever had amalgam fillings or dental sealant in your teeth?</p>	<p>This question is used to identify persons with amalgam fillings and dental sealant. They may need to be treated separately in some analysis. Amalgam fillings could be a source of exposure to metals, including mercury.</p>	<p>Please note that a filling is expected to last for as many as ten years, whereas the average life expectancy of a dental sealant is no longer than a year. Sealants are usually provided to children. If person reports that he/she has any amalgam fillings, the number of teeth which have the filling should be recorded as the time when the filling was last time placed/removed.</p>

4.7 Mycotoxins

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
<p>1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to mycotoxins.</p>	<p>Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>
<p>2. Do you have or have recently had any of the following problems in your home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on mould growth, humidity in the house or mouldy odour since this could be a route of exposure to mycotoxins through inhalation.</p>	<p>Please ask if there are domestic problems related to mould on walls, water damage, mouldy odour.</p>
<p>3. Does your house has a ventilation system? If yes, are there filters change? How frequent?</p>	<p>Mechanical ventilation at home is related with the exposure to circulating compounds and aerosols (including mycotoxins), increasing the indoor concentrations of these compounds at home, and consequently to human exposure through inhalation.</p>	<p>Please ask if there is a ventilation system and in affirmative case if it includes filter change and which is the frequency of its change.</p>
Diet		

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the main dietary predictors of the exposure to mycotoxins.</p>	<p>Please note that the period of interest is 4 weeks in order to assess the typical diet. Think about all the food/beverage you eat/drink, both meals and snacks, either at home or outside, please specify all amount of foods you consumed including also ingredients of any meal (e.g. salad for sandwiches, cheese for pasta or sandwiches...)</p> <p>Please, show Annex to this manual “Food serving sizes gallery” to the interviewee to check the serving sizes of each food consumed in the last 4 weeks (at the end of this interviewer manual). Indicate the frequency of consumption of each food, as well as the number of servings, according to the pictures included in the gallery.</p>
<p>2. Have you special diet restrictions? Which?</p>	<p>This question is to identify particular vulnerable populations that could be specially exposed to mycotoxins (vegetarian, celiac, etc.)</p>	<p>Please specify the specific diet restriction (vegetarian, celiac, etc.) since some health disorders (intestinal inflammatory; food allergies) could be associated with restricted diets.</p>
Lifestyle		
<p>1. Are you involved in farming activities (animal production, greenhouse and others)?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information related to farming activities since several related activities are associated to mycotoxins exposure (animal production, greenhouse and others) through dermic contact and inhalation.</p>	<p>Please evaluate the involvement of the interviewee in farming activities. Do not consider here professional tasks.</p>
Occupation		
<p>1. From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to mycotoxins.</p>	<p>Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with pesticides. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).</p>
<p>2. Mycotoxin exposure history: in your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)?</p>	<p>The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to mycotoxins.</p>	<p>Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Health		
1. Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?	This question is aimed to obtain information on diseases or conditions associated with mycotoxins exposure: -liver diseases, -inflammatory intestinal diseases (bowel disease, Chron's disease, ulcerative colitis, stomach ulcers), -renal diseases -allergies: asthma, food allergies, recurrent apnea or pneumonia, cough, wheezing -acute pulmonar hemorrhhea -infertility, -gastric disorders (vomiting, nausea, diarrhea, abdominal pain, fever, headaches).	Please specify if interviewee suffered any of these diseases or disorders in hepatic, gastrointestinal, urinary and immune systems.
1.1 Do you have or have had cancer? If yes, what kind?	This question is aimed to obtain information on cancer associated with mycotoxins exposure (hepatic, gastrointestinal, esophageal, urinary).	Please specify cancers that could be related to exposure to mycotoxins.
2. Are you pregnant at present?	This question is to identify if mother could be exposed to mycotoxins (since early-life exposure of babies could be affected by mycotoxins)	Please specify if mother could be exposed to mycotoxins through different exposure routes (food, inhalation, dermic contact; occupational settings)
3. Are you breastfeeding?	This question is to assess if mother could transfer mycotoxins through breastfeeding.	Please specify if mother is breastfeeding only or with supplementation.

4.8 Pesticides

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
1. Is your home close to...?	It is necessary to collect information on facilities/places considered as potential sources of exposure to pesticides.	Please, consider the categories provided (no/yes < 500m./yes,500-1000 m./yes>1000m).

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
2. Does your house have garden and/or vegetable garden?	Is essential to collect information on the presence of a garden or vegetable garden at home, as well as on the use of products to fumigate, since they could be a potential source of exposure to pesticides.	If the answer is "No", all the sub-questions under questions no.2 (2.1 to 2.6) can be skipped. If the answer is "Yes", please complete all of the sub-questions.
2.1 Has your garden/vegetable garden been fumigated with pesticides and/or insecticides in the last 12 months?		Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides in the last 12 months is required.
2.2 If yes, please specify how often these products were used to fumigate		Please, specify the frequency in which these products were used during the last 12 months.
2.3 Do you usually store pesticides/insecticides used to fumigate the garden/vegetable garden at home?		Please, specify where the products used are usually stored.
2.4 How long do you usually wait to have contact with the garden/vegetable garden after the fumigation?		This question refers to the time that usually elapses between the fumigation and the use of the garden/vegetable garden by the interviewee.
2.5 Has your garden/vegetable garden been fumigated with pesticides and/or insecticides in the last week?		Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides in the last week is required.
2.6 Do you know the commercial name of these products?		If yes, please specify the commercial name of the products used in that period.
3. Has your house (inside) or your workplace been fumigated with pesticides and/or insecticides in the last 12 months?	The use of pesticides/insecticides at the workplace/house could be associated with increased levels of exposure to pesticides. Different timeframes are considered here, due to the wide variety of substances encompassed by "pesticides", and the potential differences affecting their half-life.	Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides at workplace/house (inside) in the last 12 months is required.
3.1 Has your house (inside) or your workplace been fumigated with pesticides and/or insecticides in the last 4 weeks?		Here, the use of pesticides/insecticides at workplace/house (inside) in the last 4 weeks is required.
3.2 Do you know the commercial name of the products used to fumigate your home/workplace?		If yes, please specify the commercial name of the products used in the mentioned places.
4. Do you have or have recently had any of the following pest problems in your home?	Pest problems at home are usually treated by using pesticides, which could affect the exposure levels to these substances in people living in the residence.	Provide here information on pest problems that have occurred at home. Specify other problems if they are not explicitly mentioned in the question.
5. In the last 12 months, were insecticide products used to control or repel insects at your home? Please consider insecticide sprays, tablets, liquids etc.	Domestic products to repel insects could be a source of exposure to pesticides at home.	This question refers to domestic products such as sprays, liquids, tablets, used in the last 12 months.
6. Did you have any pets at home in the last 12 months? If yes, specify type and number	Pets are considered as a source of home exposure to certain compounds, including	Indicate the type(s) and number of animals living at home.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
6.1. In the last month, were any of the following products used for your pets?	pesticides, because of the deposition or accumulation of these substances in the hair. Likewise, the use of products for pets, including insecticides, could be also a source of exposure to these substances.	Specify which products were applied to the animals in the last month. This mainly includes antiparasitic agents (lotions, spray..).
7. How often is general cleaning done in your home?	House cleaning is associated with the concentration of substances, including chemical pollutants inside home, including pesticides. This variable might affect human exposure indoors, since house cleaning involves the mobilization and elimination of dust-borne chemicals deposited in floor, windows, etc.	Please note that general cleaning refers to a wide cleaning in the whole dwelling involving floors, dust, regardless of the person involved on this task.
8. Do you use a vacuum cleaner for general cleaning of your home? If yes, please, specify type and frequency of use	The use of vacuum cleaner for house cleaning involves the mobilization of substances accumulated in domestic dust. This might affect the concentrations of circulating compounds inside home (e.g pesticides), and therefore, the exposure of residents to these compounds.	Please, indicate if a vacuum cleaner is used for house cleaning. When appropriate, specify the frequency of use, as well as the type of filter. Note that water filters refer to those vacuum cleaners having a container for water, while air filters do not need water for working but a bag or a tank where the dust is accumulated.
9. How is your house usually ventilated? For each option, please, specify frequency of use (months/year in which mechanical systems are used; hours/day for window ventilation by season)	Ventilation at home (mechanical or manual) is related with the exchange of circulating compounds, including pesticides, affecting to indoor concentrations of these compounds at home, and consequently to human exposure levels.	Please, ask for ways of the ventilation of home, and their frequency of use. Please note that mechanical ventilation usually entails the presence of electromechanical systems (e.g. fans) to drive air flow inside and outside home. In case this mechanical system is automatically working, then indicate Always working in the questionnaire.
Diet		
1. How often did you consume the following food items in the last 4 weeks?	Exposure to pesticides through the diet can be associated with a wide variety of meals (fruit, vegetables, cereals...). It is important to consider all the main groups of meals to assess, in an accuracy way, their contribution on the exposure levels to pesticides.	It is recommended to consider all food items from the general diet section.
2. How do you usually treat vegetables and fruits before consuming?	This question aims to evaluate if some treatments could be associated with increased or decreased levels of exposure to exposure to pesticides.	Please, indicate how fruits and vegetables are usually treated before consuming.
3. What type of vegetables and fruits do you usually eat?	The maturation stage of fruits could be associated with differences in the exposure levels to pesticides.	Please, indicate how fruits and vegetables are usually consumed, regarding the maturation stage.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
4. How do you usually eat vegetables and fruits?	This question aims to identify potential differences in the exposure levels to pesticides associated with the consumption of fruit with or without skin.	Please, indicate how fruits and vegetables are usually consumed (with or without skin).
5. Where do you usually buy vegetables and fruits?	The origin of vegetables and fruits could lead to different exposure levels to pesticides in humans. Likewise, this question aims to assess potential differences between local products and products with other origin, regarding their contribution on the levels of exposure to pesticides in humans.	Please, specify the main origin of the fruits/vegetables consumed by the interviewee.
6. Did you consume organic food in the last 6 months?	Organic diet has been found to be associated with decreased level of exposure to pesticides in humans.	Information on the consumption of organic food in the last 6 months (including the main groups of meals) will be collected here. Please note that organic food can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate organic from non-organic food.
6.1 How often did you usually consume organic food in the last 6 months?		
6.2 Which percentage of your diet is based on organic food? Indicate a percentage for each of the following food items (0%= nothing organic and 100%= all the food consumed is organic)		
7. Did you eat home-grown vegetables, fruit and/or herbs in the last 6 months? If yes, indicate per season the portion you have eaten home-grown products (0%= nothing and 100%= all fruit/vegetable is home-grown)	This question aims to assess the effect of eating home-grown vegetables, fruit and/or herbs could on the exposure levels to pesticides in humans.	If yes, specify the percentage of home-grown vegetables, fruit and/or herbs consumed by the interviewee in each of the seasons.
Lifestyle		
1. Did you use insect repellents or anti-parasite products for human use, including lotions, sprays, shampoos etc. in the last 6 months? If not, go to question 2	Insect repellents for human use generally include in their compositions a wide variety of substances, including certain types of pesticides. The use of these products might lead to an increase in the exposure levels to these compounds.	Please, specify if anti-parasite products for humans have been used by the interviewee in the last 6 months, and the frequency of use.
1.1. How often did you use these products in the last 6 months?		
2. Did you carry out one of the following DIY activities or hobbies and/or did you use one of the following products performing these DIY activities or hobbies in the last month? (please, do not count your professional activity).	Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to pesticides and its compounds. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to pesticides.	Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know.

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
3. Did you have contact with poultry in the last 6 months?	Although the evidence is still limited, poultry could be a vector of transmission of certain pesticides used to control pest in poultry farms.	Poultry refers to a group of domestic birds, which includes chickens, turkeys, ducks, among others. This questions refers to the last 6 months.
Occupation		
1. From the following list of working tasks/activities, please, indicate if you perform them in carrying out your job, the duration and frequency in a work shift, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures:	The question is aimed to obtain an overall and complete overview of the participants' exposure conditions and their potential association with levels of exposure to pesticides.	Please, specify the work task where you come into contact with pesticides. Specify compounds (name, CAS-number, etc.).
2. Pesticide exposure history: in your previous jobs have you performed any of the following working tasks/activities (if yes, please, indicate the total period of exposure, the use of PPE and the availability of collective protective measures)?	The question is aimed to obtain information on past jobs and their potential association with levels of exposure to pesticides.	Please, specify if you were exposed to these substances. If applicable, indicate the period of exposure and the use of PPE.
Health		
1. Did you suffer of any of the following symptoms and/or signs in the last 5 years (if yes please specify the frequency)?	It is important to collect information on those symptoms found to be associated with the exposure to pesticides.	The timeframe of this question refers to the last 5 years. Please, specify if the interviewee suffered any of this symptoms, if yes, specify the frequency.
2. Have you ever been diagnosed with a pesticide poisoning?	Pesticide poisoning could lead to increased levels of exposure to pesticides.	Only include pesticide poisoning diagnosed by a medical doctor.

4.9 UV Filters (Benzophenones)

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
Residential environment and home exposures		
<p>1. Is there any of the following facilities within 300 m of you home?</p>	<p>It is necessary to collect information on facilities considered as potential sources of exposure to UV Filters-Benzophenones.</p>	<p>Please, ask only for those facilities located near the participant's home (300 m). Multiple answers are possible. If the concept of distance is not well understood by the interviewee, some explanation can be given as: "facilities within 15 minutes walking distance from your home". When appropriate (e.g. facilities not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of other facilities located near household.</p>
<p>2. What materials are most of the floor covering your home made of?</p>	<p>The floor covering is considered as an important source of indoor exposure to certain compounds, especially benzophenones. Furthermore, floor covering favouring dust accumulation could be a way for humans to be exposed to other pollutants at home.</p>	<p>This question aims to collect information on the main type of materials used to cover more than 50% of the floor. When appropriate (e.g. floor covering not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), specify the name of other floor coverings given by the interviewee. If a clear response is not obtained, then select Don't Know. Synthetic or natural fiber with plastic backing refers to fiber that is fixed on a flat, sometimes bendable surface made out of a rubber or plastic. This surface is often not seen easily as it is the layer applied to the ground (the backside or backing), with the fiber side facing upwards.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>3. In the last month, were any of the cleaning products listed below used in your home, at least once a week? If yes, please specify if the cleaning product generally used is a chemical or eco-friendly product</p>	<p>Certain household cleaning products contain chemical substances which residents could be exposed to (e.g. Benzophenones). Hence, a proper characterization of the exposure via questionnaire to these products is needed to identify their potential contribution on human exposure.</p>	<p>This question aims to identify those products used at home at least once a week in the last month, irrespective of the person in charge of their application. For those products used, please specify if it is a chemical or eco-friendly product. Eco-friendly products refer to those products without chemical substances in their composition (or reduced concentrations). They can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don't know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate chemical from eco-friendly products. If applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure of the right category), specify the name of product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee does not have a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know.</p>
<p>4. Are scents and flavouring substances usually used in [this flat/house], (e.g. fragrance lamps, joss sticks, air fresheners and fragrance dispensers)?</p>	<p>The use of flavouring substances at home could lead to increase the levels of exposure to benzophenones in people living in the residence.</p>	<p>Please, indicate the frequency of use of flavouring substances at home, including all the variety of these products.</p>
<p>5. How often is general cleaning done in your home?</p>	<p>House cleaning is associated with the concentration of substances, including chemical pollutants inside home, including benzophenones. This variable might affect human exposure indoors, since house cleaning involves the mobilization and elimination of dust-borne chemicals deposited in floor, windows, etc.</p>	<p>Please note that general cleaning refers to a wide cleaning in the whole dwelling involving floors, dust, regardless of the person involved on this task.</p>
<p>6. How often do you do your laundry?</p>	<p>Benzophenones are usually added to laundry products as a perfume compound. Hence, it could be a source of exposure to these substances in humans.</p>	<p>Please, specify the laundry frequency.</p>
Diet		
<p>1. In the last 4 weeks, did you consume fast food (please consider also beverages)? If yes: how was it packed and how often did you consume it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates exposure to food contact materials possibly containing benzophenones</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of food contact materials.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>2. Do you drink beverages different from water (fruit juices, ice tea, soft drinks...)? If yes, specify which of the following bottling types do you usually consume (Multiple answers possible)</p>	<p>This question assesses the possible exposure to benzophenones from food contact materials through food/beverage (cross contamination). Often, liquid containers have a cap or an internal layer made out of plastic that is in contact with the liquid they contain. This is why bottled water can potentially be also a source of benzophenones.</p>	<p>Please note that participants can select multiple type of food contact materials.</p>
<p>3. Do you use the following containers for keeping food in the refrigerators or for longer-time storage elsewhere? If yes, how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to benzophenones from food contact materials.</p>	<p>Please note that information on the use of each type of containers has to be collected. Containers used for general food storage (cold and non-cold storage) are included here.</p>
<p>4. Do you use the following containers for preparing or heating food in the microwave oven? If yes: how often do you use it?</p>	<p>This question evaluates the possible exposure to benzophenones from food contact materials (cross contamination).</p>	<p>Please note that multiple answers are possible. .</p>
Lifestyle		
<p>1. How often did you use the following cosmetic and hygiene products in the last month? For each product, please indicate if possible the commercial brand you mostly use.</p>	<p>Personal care products and cosmetics are widely used. Complete information on the use of these products is needed to a proper characterization of the exposure to benzophenones in humans. The use of perfumes and other cosmetics could be associated with the exposure to benzophenones.</p>	<p>Complete information on personal care products and cosmetic used by the interviewee in the last month has to be collected. For each listed product, please indicate yes/no, and the commercial brand for those used by the interviewees. If the interviewee cannot give an answer for a product, please invite him/her to check whether the mentioned product is available at home at the time of the interview. The best would be to show a list of the cosmetic products in question and let the participant to read it along with the interviewer. This would make it easier and quicker to point out the cosmetic items used.</p>
<p>2. If sun cream or sun screen is used: which type of sun cream or sunscreen do you normally use?</p>	<p>Information on the use of sun screen will be collected, since benzophenones can be found in these personal care products.</p>	<p>Information on the type(s) of sun cream usually used will be collected here.</p>
<p>3. If sun screen is used: how do you apply sunscreen that you usually use? As a...</p>		<p>Information on how the sun cream is usually applied will be collected here.</p>

QUESTIONS	JUSTIFICATION	INFORMATION FOR INTERVIEWERS
<p>4. What type of personal care products do you mostly use?</p>	<p>This question aims to identify the potential effect of using chemical and eco-friendly products on the exposure levels to benzophenones.</p>	<p>Please note that <i>Eco-friendly</i> products refer to those products without chemical substances in their composition (or reduced concentrations). They can be identified by the labelled and specifications in their packaging. Please, select “don’t know” if the interviewee is unable to differentiate chemical from <i>eco-friendly</i> products. If the interviewee does not have a clear response about the origin of these products, then select Don't Know.</p>
<p>5. Did you carry out any of the following activities as DIY activities or hobbies and/or were you exposed to any of these substances in these activities in the last month? (Please, do not count your professional activity).</p>	<p>Some hobbies and DIY activities involve the use of certain products which could affect exposure to pesticides and its compounds. This question will help to explore the relationship between the products used in the last month and the exposure levels to benzophenones.</p>	<p>Please note that this question refers to exposures occurred in the last month. For each group of products, indicate if they have been used by the interviewee. When applicable (e.g. a product not included in the given options or not sure about the right category), then select other products and specify the name of the product given by the interviewee. If the interviewee has not a clear response about the use of a product, then select Don't Know.</p>
Health		
<p>1. Which over the counter medicines (including antihistamines) do you use?</p>	<p>Information on medicines, including antihistamines, is required, since benzophenones can be used in the manufacturing of antihistamines and, therefore, could be a predictor of the exposure to these substances.</p>	<p>Use of medicines will be reported here. Participants will be invited to check the package leaflet of the medicinal product before answering questions concerning medicines.</p>
<p>2. Do you use glasses and/or contact eye lenses?</p>	<p>Glasses and/or contact lenses could be a potential source of exposure to benzophenones.</p>	<p>Use of glasses or contact lenses has to be collected here.</p>

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Annex 1.3.1

Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria

WP 7

Task 7.3

D 7.6

Annex A

Summary table of ISCED 2011 codes and criteria

The units of the ISCED classification are education programmes and their related recognised qualifications.

<http://www.uis.unesco.org/Education/Pages/international-standard-classification-of-education.aspx>

The ISCED classification uses **3 digits**: the **first is the educational level**, the **second** and **third are complementary dimensions**.

The ISCED level of an education programme reflects the degree of complexity and specialisation of the content of the programme measured with respect to gradations of learning experiences and the knowledge, skills and competencies the programme is intended to impart. Educational attainment is measured with respect to the highest education programme successfully completed, which is normally certified by a recognised qualification. If the highest education programme is not successfully completed, the level of attainment of the person is their attainment level before entering the programme.

LEVELS AND COMPLEMENTARY DIMENSIONS OF THE INTERNATIONAL STANDARD CLASSIFICATION OF EDUCATION (ISCED) 2011

Codification of education programmes and educational attainment

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
No education		–	–
0	Early childhood education	<i>Learning stimulated</i> by environment (§105)* or in interaction with educators (§106).	<i>Qualifications of staff</i> : Pedagogical qualifications for educators (§111).
		<i>Institution</i> : school-based or centre-based (§107)	Existence of a regulatory framework (§112).
		<i>Admission/age</i> : 3 years and above for pre-primary education (§102/108).	Typically not compulsory (§113).
		<i>Intensity</i> : 2 hours of education per day and 100 days a year (§110).	
1	Primary education	<i>Education</i> with systematic teaching and learning in reading, writing and mathematics (§125).	Often coincides with the beginning of compulsory education (§127).
		<i>Admission/age and duration</i> : official age of entry between ages 5 and 7 years; typical duration of 6 years (range is 4 to 7 years) (§122).	
		<i>Teacher</i> : typically one main teacher is in charge of a group (§126).	
2	Lower secondary education	<i>Transition to subject-oriented instruction</i> (§144).	<i>Typical entry age</i> is between 10 and 13 years, the most common being 12 (§141).
		<i>Entry requirements</i> : completion of primary education (or the capacity to study at ISCED level 2) (§145).	<i>Subject teachers</i> , with qualifications in specific subjects as well as pedagogy (§147).
		<i>Cumulative duration</i> : ends after 8 to 11 years of education (often 9) from the start of primary education (§146).	The end of the level often coincides with the <i>end of compulsory education</i> (§148).

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions				Coding		
2 nd digit		3 rd digit		Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/HATVOC**
-		-		-	010	000
Type of education:						
1	Early childhood educational development (0 to 2 years)	-	-	010	020	-
2	Pre-primary education (from 3 years to the start of primary education)	-	-	020		000
-	-	-	-	100	100	100
Programme orientation:			Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:			
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion or partial level completion (duration < 2 years or cumulative duration < 8 years since the start of ISCED level 1).	241, 251	100	100
		2	Partial level completion (intermediate programme with duration ≥ 2 years and cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	242, 252	242, 252	200
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	243, 253	243, 253	200
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 8 years).	244, 254	244, 254	200

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
3	Upper secondary education	<i>Second/final stage of secondary education, in form of general or vocational programmes (§167).</i>	<i>More differentiated programmes: increased range of options and streams (§169).</i>
		<i>Entry requirements: completion of lower secondary education (or the capacity to study at ISCED level 3) (§168).</i>	<i>Teachers often more qualified with respect to the subject matter they teach than lower secondary teachers (§170).</i>
		<i>Cumulative duration: programmes end 12 or 13 years since the beginning of ISCED 1 (§164).</i>	
4	Post-secondary non-tertiary education	<i>Post-secondary education, generally vocational and terminal programmes preparing for the labour market; typically, not considered as tertiary education at the national level (§190).</i>	
		<i>Programmes which serve to broaden rather than deepen the knowledge, skills and competencies of participants. Often not significantly more advanced than programmes at ISCED level 3 (§191).</i>	
		<i>Entry requirements: completion of upper secondary education (§186).</i>	
5	Short-cycle tertiary education	<i>Programmes often designed to provide participants with professional knowledge, skills and competencies; may provide pathway to academic programmes (§207). More complex than levels 3 and 4 but less than 6 (§212).</i>	<i>Institutional transition points: often provided by different institutions from ISCED levels 6, 7 and 8 (§214).</i>
		<i>Entry requirements: successful completion of upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education giving access to ISCED levels 5, 6 or 7 (§208)</i>	
		<i>Minimum duration: 2 years (§213).</i>	<i>Typical duration: 2 to 3 years (§213).</i>

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions			Coding			
2 nd digit	3 rd digit		Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/ HATVOC**	
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion or partial level completion (duration < 2 years or cumulative duration < 11 years since the start of ISCED level 1).	341, 351	244, 254	200
		2	Partial level completion (intermediate programme with duration ≥ 2 years and cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	342, 352	342, 352	302/1, 302/2
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 3 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	343, 353	343, 353	303/1, 303/2
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7 (duration ≥ 2 years, cumulative duration ≥ 11 years).	344, 354	344, 354	304/1, 304/2
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration < 6 months)	441, 451	344 354	300/1, 300/2
5	Vocational	3	Level completion without direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7	443, 453	443, 453	400/1, 400/2
		4	Level completion with direct access to ISCED 5, 6 or 7	444, 454	444, 454	
Programme orientation:		Level completion and access to higher ISCED level:				
4	General (or academic)	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration < 2 years)	541, 551	444, 454	400
5	Vocational (or professional)	4	Level completion	544, 554	540, 550	500

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Level		Criteria for classifying national programmes by levels	
1 st digit		Main criteria	Subsidiary criteria
6	Bachelor's or equivalent	Programmes often designed to provide participants with intermediate academic or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a first degree, such as a <i>Bachelor's</i> , or to an equivalent qualification (§224).	The requirement of a doctorate (ISCED level 8) qualification for some of the teaching staff may help distinguish ISCED levels 5 and 6 (§231).
		<i>Entry requirements:</i> successful completion of upper secondary or post-secondary non-tertiary education giving access to ISCED levels 5, 6 or 7; may require the passing of an entrance examination (§226).	<i>Further studies:</i> does not give direct access (usually) to doctoral programmes (ISCED level 8) (§226).
		<i>Minimum cumulative duration of first degrees:</i> 3 to 4 years full-time (§229).	
		<i>Position in the national degree structure:</i> typically a first degree in tertiary education; sometimes a second degree of 1 to 2 years (§230).	
7	Master's or equivalent	Programmes often designed to provide participants with advanced academic or professional knowledge, skills and competencies, leading to a second degree, such as a <i>Master's</i> , or to an equivalent qualification (§241).	<i>Minimum duration of long 1st degree:</i> 5 years; complexity of content comparable to a <i>Master's</i> (§247).
		<i>Position in the national degree structure:</i> typically a second or further degree in tertiary education following a first degree at ISCED level 6 or 7 (§246) or a long first degree of at least 5 years if equivalent to a <i>Master's</i> in terms of the complexity of content (e.g. medicine) (§247).	<i>Further studies:</i> often gives direct access to doctoral programmes (ISCED level 8) (§249).
		<i>Entry requirements:</i> in the case of a 2 nd degree, the successful completion of a <i>Bachelor's</i> or equivalent (ISCED level 6) or a <i>Master's</i> or equivalent (ISCED level 7) is required; in the case of a 1 st degree, the successful completion of upper secondary or of ISCED 4 granting access to tertiary education is required and, eventually, an entry examination (§243).	
8	Doctoral or equivalent	Its successful completion requires the <i>submission of a thesis</i> or an equivalent written work, of publishable quality, which is the output of original research representing a considerable contribution to knowledge in the field (§264).	Degree gives access to faculty positions and research posts (§266).
		<i>Entry requirements:</i> the successful completion of an ISCED 7 programme (§261).	
		<i>Minimum duration:</i> at least 3 years of full-time studies and a total cumulative duration of at least 7 years of tertiary education (§265)	

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

Complementary dimensions				Coding		
2 nd digit		3 rd digit		Education programmes ISCED-P (Annex II of ISCED 2011)	Educational attainment ISCED-A (Annex III of ISCED 2011)	EU Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL/HATVOC**
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 3 years)	641, 651, 661	540, 550	500
5	Professional	5	First degree (at Bachelor's level) (duration 3 to 4 years)	645, 655, 665	640, 650, 660	600
6	Unspecified	6	Long first degree (at Bachelor's level) (duration > 4 years)	646, 656, 666		
		7	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Bachelor's level)	647, 657, 667		
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 5 years)	741, 751, 761	640, 650, 660	600
5	Professional	6	Long first degree (at Master's level) (duration ≥ 5 years)	746, 756, 766	740, 750, 760	700
6	Unspecified	7	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Bachelor's level)	747, 757, 767		
		8	Second or further degree (following a 1 st degree at Master's level)	748, 758, 768		
Programme orientation:		Position in the national degree and qualification structure:				
4	Academic	1	Insufficient for level completion (duration of first degree < 3 years)	841, 851, 861	740, 750, 760	700
5	Professional	4	Level completion	844, 854, 864	840, 850, 860	800
6	Unspecified					

Notes

* Paragraph numbers are references to the main ISCED 2011 classification document. See more details in the Reader's Guide.

** European Union Labour Force Survey variable HATLEVEL / HATVOC (European Commission Regulation 317/2013).

From:

ISCED 2011 Operational Manual

Guidelines for Classifying National Education Programmes and Related Qualifications

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Annex 1.3.2

Definitions of major groups, sub-major groups, ISCO

2008

WP7

Task 7.3

D 7.6

**STRUCTURE OF THE INTERNATIONAL
STANDARD CLASSIFICATION OF
OCCUPATIONS (ISCO-08)**

Major Groups

- 1 Managers
- 2 Professionals
- 3 Technicians and Associate Professionals
- 4 Clerical Support Workers
- 5 Services and Sales Workers
- 6 Skilled Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Workers
- 7 Craft and Related Trades Workers
- 8 Plant and Machine Operators and Assemblers
- 9 Elementary Occupations
- 0 Armed Forces Occupations

MAJOR AND SUB-MAJOR GROUPS

1 Managers

- 11 Chief Executives, Senior Officials and Legislators
- 12 Administrative and Commercial Managers
- 13 Production and Specialized Services Managers
- 14 Hospitality, Retail and Other Services Managers

2 Professionals

- 21 Science and Engineering Professionals
- 22 Health Professionals
- 23 Teaching Professionals
- 24 Business and Administration Professionals
- 25 Information and Communications Technology Professionals
- 26 Legal, Social and Cultural Professionals

3 Technicians and Associate Professionals

- 31 Science and Engineering Associate Professionals
- 32 Health Associate Professionals
- 33 Business and Administration Associate Professionals
- 34 Legal, Social, Cultural and Related Associate Professionals
- 35 Information and Communications Technicians

4 Clerical Support Workers

- 41 General and Keyboard Clerks
- 42 Customer Services Clerks
- 43 Numerical and Material Recording Clerks
- 44 Other Clerical Support Workers

5 Services and Sales Workers

- 51 Personal Services Workers
- 52 Sales Workers
- 53 Personal Care Workers
- 54 Protective Services Workers

6 Skilled Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Workers

- 61 Market-oriented Skilled Agricultural Workers
- 62 Market-oriented Skilled Forestry, Fishery and Hunting Workers
- 63 Subsistence Farmers, Fishers, Hunters and Gatherers

7 Craft and Related Trades Workers

71 Building and Related Trades Workers (excluding Electricians)

72 Metal, Machinery and Related Trades Workers

73 Handicraft and Printing Workers

74 Electrical and Electronic Trades Workers

75 Food Processing, Woodworking, Garment and Other Craft and Related Trades Workers

8 Plant and Machine Operators and Assemblers

81 Stationary Plant and Machine Operators

82 Assemblers

83 Drivers and Mobile Plant Operators

9 Elementary Occupations

91 Cleaners and Helpers

92 Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Labourers

93 Labourers in Mining, Construction, Manufacturing and Transport

94 Food Preparation Assistants

95 Street and Related Sales and Services Workers

96 Refuse Workers and Other Elementary Workers

0 Armed Forces Occupations

01 Commissioned Armed Forces Officers

02 Non-commissioned Armed Forces Officers

03 Armed Forces Occupations, Other Ranks

Isco 08. International standard classification of occupations. Structure, group definitions and correspondence tables.

Available at: <https://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/isco08/>

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Annex 1.3.3

Food serving sizes gallery

WP 7

Task 7.3

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FOOD SERVING SIZES GALLERY

Pictures included in this gallery will be used to answer food consumption frequency questionnaire. These pictures will help to collect accurate measurements of serving sizes consumed by the participants. Please, indicate the number of servings of each food item consumed in the last 4 weeks, according to the relationship with the food picture.

I. FISH

WHITE FISH

Serving: two medium units (125 g)

Serving: one medium unit (130 g)

BLUE FISH (BIG SIZE)

Serving: one unit (steak, 125 g)

BLUE FISH (SMALL SIZE)

Serving: 10-15 units (225 g)

Serving: 4 units (250 g)

SALMON

Serving: one piece (130 g)

CEPHALOPODS (e.g squid, octopus)

Serving: one médium unit (100 g)

TINNED FISH

Serving: one can (60 g)

FISH FINGERS

Serving: 4 units (100 g)

CRUSTACEANS AND SHELLFISH (lobster, crayfish, scampi, crab, prawns, oysters, mussels, ...)

Serving: 15 units (100 g)

Serving: 15 units (200 g)

II. MEAT

WHITE MEAT (poultry, turkey etc...)

Serving: one thigh (290 g)

Serving: 4 units (100 g)

RED MEAT (pork, beef)

Serving: one unit (100 g)

Serving: 4 units (100 g)

Serving: one unit (90-100 g)

Serving: 2 units (100 g)

III. DAIRY PRODUCTS (NOT SKIMMED) AND EGGS

BUTTER

Serving: oneteaspoon (10 g)

MILK

Serving: one medium glass (200 ml)

CHEESE

Serving: 3 units (40 g)

Serving: 2 units (40 g)

YOGURT AND SIMILARS

Serving: one unit (125 g)

Serving: one unit (125 g)

EGGS

Serving: 2 units (120 g)

IV. CEREALS

Bread (White and Whole grain)

Serving: 2 units (100 g)

Cereal products (crackers, rusk, etc...)

Serving: 3 units (40 g)

Serving: half commercial packet(50 g)

OTHER CEREALS

Serving: 2 handfuls (30 g)

Serving: 2 handfuls (30 g)

Serving: one unit (25 g)

PASTA

Serving: half a coffee cup (75 g)

Serving: 75 g

RICE

Serving: half a coffee cup (75 g)

FATS

V. VEGETABLES AND FRUITS

CARROTS

Serving: 2 units (200 g)

FRESH TOMATOES

Serving: 2 units (200 g)

LEAFY VEGETABLES

Serving: 4 handfuls (200 g)

Serving: 10 units (200 g)

BROCCOLI

Serving: 1/3 unit (200 g)

GREEN BEANS

Serving: 10-15 units (200 g)

CHIPS/FRENCH FRIES

Serving: 100 g

MUSHROOMS

Serving: 8 units (200 g)

ONION

Serving: one unit (200-250 g)

SOYBEANS

Serving: one handful (20 g)

TINNED PRODUCTS (e.g. vegetables, legumes, cereals)

Serving: one can (150 g)

Serving: 9 units (200 g)

FRESH FRUITS

Serving: one unit (150-200 g)

Serving: one slice (150-170g)

Serving: one slice (200 g)

Serving: 5-7 units (200 g)

FRUIT JUICES

Serving: one glass or individual brick (200 ml)

VI. SNACKS

Popcorn (microwave or home-made)

Serving: one bowl (30 g)

PEANUTS

Serving: 2 tablespoons (30 g)

ICECREAMS

Serving: one unit (75 g)

Serving: one piece (two fingers thick, 60 g or 100 ml)

POTATO CHIPS

Serving: one bowl (50 g)

JELLY CANDIES

Serving: 20 units (30 g)

HAZELNUT SPREAD

Serving: one tablespoon (20-30 g)

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Pictures and information of this gallery are online available at: <http://www.insidemyfood.com>

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Annex 1.3.4

**The Statistical classification of economic activities in
the European Community, abbreviated as NACE (Type
of industry/workplace)**

WP 7

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ANNEX IV Type of industry/workplace

A – Agriculture, forestry and fishing;

- 01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities
- 02 Forestry and logging
- 03 Fishing and aquaculture

B – Mining and quarrying;

- 05 Mining of coal and lignite
- 06 Extraction of crude petroleum and natural gas
- 07 Mining of metal ores
- 08 Other mining and quarrying
- 09 Mining support service activities

C – Manufacturing;

- 10 Manufacture of food products
- 11 Manufacture of beverages
- 12 Manufacture of tobacco products
- 13 Manufacture of textiles
- 14 Manufacture of wearing apparel
- 15 Manufacture of leather and related products
- 16 Manufacture of wood and of products of wood and cork, except furniture; manufacture of particles of straw and plaiting materials
- 17 Manufacture of paper and paper products
- 18 Printing and reproduction of recorded media
- 19 Manufacture of coke and refined petroleum products
- 20 Manufacture of chemicals and chemical products
- 21 Manufacture of basic pharmaceutical products and pharmaceutical preparations
- 22 Manufacture of rubber and plastic products
- 23 Manufacture of other non-metallic mineral products
- 24 Manufacture of basic metals
- 25 Manufacture of fabricated metal products, except machinery and equipment
- 26 Manufacture of computer, electronic and optical products
- 27 Manufacture of electrical equipment
- 28 Manufacture of machinery and equipment n.e.c.
- 29 Manufacture of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers
- 30 Manufacture of other transport equipment

- 31 Manufacture of furniture
- 32 Other manufacturing
- 33 Repair and installation of machinery and equipment
- D – Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply;**
- 35 Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply

- E – Water supply, sewerage, waste management and remediation activities;**
- 36 Water collection, treatment and supply
- 37 Sewerage
- 38 Waste collection, treatment and disposal activities; materials recovery
- 39 Remediation activities and other waste management services

- F – Construction;**
- 41 Construction of buildings
- 42 Civil engineering
- 43 Specialised construction activities

- G – Wholesale and retail trade, repair of motor vehicle and motorcycles;**
- 45 Wholesale and retail trade and repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles
- 46 Wholesale trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles
- 47 Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles

- H – Transportation and storage;**
- 49 Land transport and transport via pipelines
- 50 Water transport
- 51 Air transport
- 52 Warehousing and support activities for transportation
- 53 Postal and courier activities

- I – Accommodation and food service activities;**
- 55 Accommodation
- 56 Food and beverage service activities

- J – Information and communication;**
- 58 Publishing activities
- 59 Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities
- 60 Programming and broadcasting activities
- 61 Telecommunications
- 62 Computer programming, consultancy and related activities
- 63 Information service activities

K – Financial and insurance activities;

- 64 Financial service activities, except insurance and pension funding
- 65 Insurance, reinsurance and pension funding, except compulsory social security
- 66 Activities auxiliary to financial services and insurance activities

L – Real estate activities;

- 68 Real estate activities

M – Professional, scientific and technical activities;

- 69 Legal and accounting activities
- 70 Activities of head offices; management consultancy activities
- 71 Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis
- 72 Scientific research and development
- 73 Advertising and market research
- 74 Other professional, scientific and technical activities
- 75 Veterinary activities

N – Administrative and support service activities;

- 77 Rental and leasing activities
- 78 Employment activities
- 79 Travel agency, tour operator and other reservation service and related activities
- 80 Security and investigation activities
- 81 Services to buildings and landscape activities
- 82 Office administrative, office support and other business support activities

O – Public administration and defence, compulsory social security;

- 84 Public administration and defence; compulsory social security

P – Education;

- 85 Education

Q – Human health and social work activities;

- 86 Human health activities
- 87 Residential care activities
- 88 Social work activities without accommodation

R – Arts, entertainment and recreation;

- 90 Creative, arts and entertainment activities
- 91 Libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities
- 92 Gambling and betting activities
- 93 Sports activities and amusement and recreation activities

S – Other service activities;

94 Activities of membership organisations

95 Repair of computers and personal and household goods

96 Other personal service activities

T – Activities of households as employers, undifferentiated goods – and services – producing activities of households for own use;

97 Activities of households as employers of domestic personnel

98 Undifferentiated goods- and services-producing activities of private households for own use

U – Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies.

99 Activities of extraterritorial organisations and bodies

Nace Rev. 2. Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community.

Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/products-manuals-and-guidelines/-/KS-RA-07-015>